

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network

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D1.1 Reference document with key concepts: Vision for building the network of living labs and research infrastructures for agroecology transition

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List of abbreviations

AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Information Systems
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EC	European Commission
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
HLPE	High Level Panel of Experts on Food Security and Nutrition
LL	Living Lab
OIA	Open innovation arrangements
RI	Research Infrastructure

Glossary

Term	Definition according to the ALL-Ready project
Activities	The work of a group or organisation to achieve a specific aim
Co-creation	It is the collaborative development of new value (concepts, methods and tools, solutions, products and services) in collaboration between experts and stakeholders in which inputs of the user play a central role. It represents a form of open innovation
Competencies	The capability to apply or mobilize a set of related knowledge, skills, and abilities required to successfully perform tasks in a defined work setting
Food sovereignty	A food system in which the people who produce, distribute, and consume food also control the mechanisms (social, economic) and policies of food production, distribution, consumption.
Incentives	Specific aspects (e.g. policy, economy, label) that motivate or drive persons to do something or behave in a certain way

Indicators	Specific, observable or/and measurable characteristic that can be used to monitor states, changes or progress of a program and/or a system making toward achieving a specific outcome
Meta-governance	Approach managing successful combinations of different governance styles. It produces some degree of coordinated governance, by designing a sound combinations of hierarchical, market, and network governance, to achieve the best possible outcomes.
System	<p>A group of <u>interacting</u> or interrelated elements that act according to a set of processes to form a unified whole. A system is described by its boundaries, <u>structure</u> and purpose and expressed in its functioning.</p> <p>Agroecosystems are complex systems in which many species interact, with ecological processes that take place at different spatial and temporal scales, with strong interactions between ecological and management processes, dedicated to agricultural production</p>
Territory	An area acting as a political – social – economic and/or environmental unit and for which specificities can be defined. This can be and area from few km ² to a region of a country.
Values	Used here in an ethic sense. May be described as treating actions themselves as abstract objects, putting ethic value to them. They can therefore be seen as drivers for activities.

Preface

This paper, prepared by the ALL-Ready consortium, has the aim to lay a conceptual and operational framework for the future European partnership entitled: "Accelerating farming systems transition: agroecology living labs and research infrastructures". It sets out the key principles, concepts, and criteria featuring the role of place-based open innovation arrangements as exemplified by living labs (LL) and shared research infrastructures (RI) to accelerate agroecology transition. As such, it is the foundation for the preparation of the partnership and for the partnership itself.

European context

Today there is wide recognition that "business as usual" is no longer an option. The European Green Deal sets out ambitious targets for a Europe in which:

- There are no net emissions of greenhouse gases by 2050,
- Economic growth is decoupled from resource use,
- No person and no place are left behind.

The Green Deal is to be implemented according to specific strategies, including the "Farm to Fork" and the 2030 Biodiversity strategy, that benefit from funding from the new Horizon Europe framework programme and the Common Agricultural Policy. Both the Farm to Fork and Biodiversity strategies cite agroecology as a sustainable practice and a means to reducing the use of pesticides, fertilisers and antimicrobials. Furthermore, as part of Horizon Europe, a new set of European partnerships – mobilising resources from Member States and Associated Countries and co-funded or co-programmed by the European Commission are being developed that are designed to have societal impact. Among these is one on "Accelerating farming systems transition: agroecology living labs and research infrastructures".

European partnership on Agroecology

According to the European Commission, this partnership should "accelerate the transition towards sustainable, climate and ecosystem friendly farming practices by enabling to better grasp short to long term agroecological processes from farm to landscape levels, by boosting place-based innovation in co-creative environments ensuring farmers and other key stakeholders' engagement (including consumers) and by improving the flow and uptake of knowledge and innovations on Agroecology across Europe". The rationale for this partnership is that strongly linking agriculture to ecological processes and biodiversity will render it more sustainable and resilient and to do this, a real-life approach, involving all actors, as exemplified in living labs, in a science-based and open science context, as exemplified in RI, will ensure that this is not just an academic exercise. Agroecology is defined by the European Commission as "the science of ecological processes applied to agricultural production systems" although as can be seen below, it is not so simple.

Although agroecology is not a new concept, today it is defined as a set of practices, a science and a movement and as such is open to different interpretations. Furthermore, the concept of living labs is still relatively new and therefore requires a new way at looking at research programming and funding. Various RI have been established at national and European levels and their research and development services have extended to more diverse actors with the opening of science. RI dealing with agriculture, food or environmental systems can really play significant roles for agroecology development, with extended missions for open-science and regarding their territorial anchorage.

The ALL-Ready project is a CSA that was selected to help prepare this European partnership. In this paper, the ALL-Ready consortium sets out to explain the key concepts of agroecology transition, living labs and research infrastructures and to describe our vision for how LLs and RIs can contribute to accelerating the above-described transition. By describing the concepts and providing a glossary of terms, we aim to clarify the concepts as the basis of a common understanding and to provide a solid foundation for the partnership.

Abstract

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs and Research Infrastructures that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality, as well as the social and economic dimensions of sustainable and resilient agroecosystems.

To build the framework of the future European network of living labs and research infrastructures that will enable the transition towards agroecology, we first pointed out the main transformations and changes of paradigms associated with agroecology, then mapped what is necessary for agroecology transition, before specifying what is expected from living labs and research infrastructures to accelerate transition.

To outline what is necessary for the agroecosystem and agri-food chain to move towards agroecology, we synthesised scientific literature (reviews and policy papers) on agroecology principles into four mind-maps: values, categories of activities and of policy incentives, and competences and skills. The four mind maps were submitted to stakeholder evaluation and inputs, then translated into synthetic tables. The main characteristics of agroecology LLs and RIs proposed according to the picture formed by the four mind maps are shown in the tables herein. A glossary has been collectively established as an outcome of this deliverable.

1. The Method

The overall method that supports the design of the conceptual framework is detailed in annex 1. The work intertwined three sources of reflexion i) research foresights in the scientific field of agroecology to identify what counts and where knowledge has to be produced, ii) the combination of a high diversity of policy recommendations to specify the activities to be synchronised at the different levels (on field, by the intermediaries, by the policy makers) and iii) the inference of how living labs and research infrastructures, thanks to their unique features, can accelerate the transition.

For each source, a mind map synthesising the literature was first submitted by the leaders of task 1.1 to the consortium for collective brainstorming to check, add and get a collective sense of ownership and choose the main dimensions to be kept in the conceptual framework (annex 1). Once the representation was clear, it was submitted to the stakeholders for evaluation during a workshop. The narrative of the overall framework in the following sessions is the product of these iterations.

2. State of the art of Agroecology

2.1 An historical trajectory of agroecology in Europe

Agroecology, first understood as integrating ecological processes in agricultural production systems, is also currently acknowledged to be at the same time a scientific field, a practice and a social movement (Wezel et al., 2009). In the European context these three dimensions each have a specific history.

Agroecology in science. In the European context, agroecology arose from the scientific sphere, and this in a pioneering way, in the 1920s, and even earlier, during a tense period (1920-1960). These are the works of Bensin, Azzi Papadakis, Friederichs, Tischler (in Olivier and Bellon, 2021). Several scientists from European countries (France, Italy, Germany) have published in this field, in parallel and quite early on, highlighting the interest of taking ecological processes into account in agricultural production processes. This period has been somewhat forgotten in the history of European agroecology. Agroecology in contemporary sciences is now booming (Caquet et al., 2021; Wezel and Bellon, 2018).

Agroecology in practice. The extension to an agroecology comprised of practices seems to have been greatly slowed down in Europe by the Second World War, due to an imperative need to feed a starving population. The agroecology of practices imposed itself later in Europe, coming from the American world where it had developed (years 1950-1970) (work by Altieri), and where it asserted itself from a very integrative viewpoint. Agroecology cannot develop without a demand from society, consistent with the needs of food consumption and their organisation into agri-food chains and territories. Some authors therefore incorporate the dimension of food systems into agroecology (Francis et al., 2003; Gliessman, 2006). This agroecology of practices has imposed itself in Europe mainly through organic farming, and this at national and European levels. Agroecology of practices has developed in response to environmental degradation, but also in response to social and economic dimensions.

Agroecology as a social movement including policy. Agroecology has gradually become institutionalised in most of the European countries through organic farming organisations. As an example, France recognised agroecology in the Agroecology Project of the French Ministry of Agriculture which was designed to encourage production methods that have high economic and environmental performance, and to promote a joint approach to the different dimensions of farms and, even further, those of agri-food chains and territories. As the first article of the Rural Code has emphasised since adoption of the law on the future of agriculture, food, and

forestry of 13 October 2014, “public policies aim to promote and sustain agroecological production systems, including organic production methods, which combine high economic and social performance, in particular through a high level of social, environmental and health protections. These systems focus on improving farm competitiveness while maintaining or improving economic profitability”. At an international level, in 2014, the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) organised the first International Symposium on Agroecology for Food Security and Nutrition with the intention of promoting agroecological systems at the international level. The 2014 symposium showed that agroecology can also be a way of rethinking agricultural systems in both developing and industrialised countries. The FAO later organized meetings by world region, including one for Europe, the conclusions of which were shared at a second symposium, in April 2018. The “Scaling Up Agroecology Initiative” was launched on this occasion¹.

The ALL-Ready project pursues this European history of agroecology, comprising within the consortium all the key concepts of the past and current development of agroecology in Europe.

2.2 The scopes of agroecology transitions to more sustainable and resilient agri-food systems

Agroecology responds to the environmental and societal issues that agricultural production must now address and contributes to strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems and land uses. In so doing, the entire agri-food system is implicated, because agricultural products (type, composition) will be different and have to be integrated in new foods and diets. It is a dynamic field of research worldwide (9 000 publications in 2018), in which ecology is associated to varying degrees with other disciplines (agronomy, genetics, social sciences, etc.; Caquet et al. 2020, see figure 1 in annex 1).

Agroecology in practice is also experimental learning, with trials and errors, and an adaptive management and governance of the agricultural and food systems, in which scientists can also be involved. It drives increased diversity of agricultural systems and consequently products, demands to revisit the norms (in socio-technical systems and agri-food value chains) and to count on local and traditional knowledge, explicit as well as implicit. Agroecology is now considered as the introduction of ecology in food systems, and concerns the local communities and the citizen in pursuit of sustainability, the use and preservation of biodiversity.

Agroecology is above all a real change in paradigm in science as well as in practices for a large number of farmers in Europe, i.e., a deep change in reasoning agricultural production and food consumption. It aims to use biological processes to meet expectations for agrosystems: agricultural production and ecosystem services (e.g., protecting resources, mitigating climate change, preserving habitats and cultural heritage). A corollary is to consider agroecology as an aim so that, through agroecological systems and practices, agroecosystems integrate the ecological functions that guarantee their own sustainability, especially in terms of replenishing nutrient stocks, controlling pests, feeding pollinators and the multiple functions for maintaining / improving production potential as well as contributing to ecosystem services. Agroecology drives in-depth transformations of agricultural and food production systems, by rethinking the mobilisation of biological processes at all levels (species, breed/variety, animal and plant physiology, feed and fertility, animal production methods and cropping practices, future of products and co-products, connections to resources, to forms of energy, to soil and water, to site specificities, etc.). Leveraging biological processes means accepting and accounting for increased diversity in agroecosystems, which leads to a greater diversity of agricultural products as well as a greater

¹ See <http://www.fao.org/3/I9049EN/i9049en.pdf>.

heterogeneity of each product that will have to be processed and included in food products (transformation process, distribution and up to new diets; see in particular figure 2 in annex 1).

The desire to use biological processes in agriculture, the underlying principle of building agroecological systems, goes along with redesigning cropping and animal breeding systems, involving changes in, for example, crop rotations and associations, plant and animal genotypes used or agricultural practices adopted, connections between plant and animal production, links to processing and distribution methods, consumption patterns, organisation of landscapes, etc. This desire makes it possible to clarify what is expected from the research community. Thus, under the terms "smart agriculture" or "sustainable agriculture", there exists a body of mainly technologically oriented studies on the best possible use of resources. This model of agriculture corresponds to "weak" agroecology, i.e. to incremental changes, which maintains continuity with current systems, neither advocating for a qualitative leap in the efficiency of the use of inputs, nor explicitly calling to replace them with biological processes (Duru *et al.*, 2014). This agroecology contrasts with "strong" agroecology, i.e. to transformational changes redesigning farming and food systems, defined by its pursuit of consistency and sustainability and by the mobilisation of biological processes (Duru *et al.*, 2014). This strong agroecology requires in-depth redesign and transformation of the agri-food chain and their organisation into territories, in line with consumption needs, as an adaptive process that is built while moving forward along a trajectory that cannot be defined in advance. Such transformation will require a significant commitment to interdisciplinary research. This should not be seen as a desire to oppose what currently exists, but should be perceived for what it is: an ambition to rethink the mobilisation of biological processes at all levels (species, breed/variety, animal and plant physiology, feed and fertility, animal production methods and cropping practices, future of products and co-products, connections to resources, to forms of energy, to soil and water, location, etc.). In such redesign, animal production is a major pillar of biological processes given its complementarities with plant production. The monitoring of processes and flows maintained in a dynamic balance from the field to the landscape, particularly for controlling pests and soil quality, lie at the heart of this redesign. A crucial driver of agroecology development is the societal demand, and often correlatively, public policies. The evolution of food consumption and the concerns of the local and territorial dimension, as pointed out by Francis *et al.*, 2003 and Gliessman, 2006, incorporate the dimension of food systems into agroecology. Agroecology can be summarised as follows: plan, create and use diversity, consider the local context and employ adaptive management that alternates between real life and theory, at all levels of the agri-food system.

The redesign is based on the implementation of principles of agroecology. One motivation for such redesign is the strengthening of the sustainability and resilience of the agroecosystems, defined as their ability to adapt to disturbances, to survive in the long term, to return to new equilibrium in a changing context. In the face of uncertainties arising from climate change and other environmental challenges, societal changes and the volatility of agricultural product and food prices, the biological diversity of agroecosystems can constitute a factor of resilience that helps dampen the effects of disturbances. The vulnerability of agroecosystems, was compensated in the past by short-term uses of inputs (pesticide, nutrients, water), and have to be now, in agroecology, compensated by biological processes (diversity, habitat, biocontrol) which allow their resilience and a greater stability of production and income.

The agroecology transition and what marks the different steps is by itself a subject of research, by analysing case studies, networks, actor behaviours, effect of new practices, new organisations, socio-technical locking, transition management, democratic governance. Supporting food sovereignty, by food autonomy or exchange, as well as offering opportunities for greater participation and co-creation, is required along the transition process. Changes in the governance of agroecosystems and farming systems is a part of the redesigning and transformational changes. The role of social and economic sciences is important. The inclusion of farmers in the production of agricultural knowledge is the key for an agroecological transition. The role of diversifying production systems and markets and value chains is also

critically important. Similarly, the inclusion of academic knowledge by using information elaborated in RI and the transformation of such information in services in an open science framework, contribute to agroecology transition (see figure 1, annex 1).

For the ALL-Ready consortium, the transformation phase that is the in-depth redesign of agroecosystems, and that of agri-food chains: itself becomes a subject of research, mobilising scientific knowledge; and constitutes a collective experience.

2.3 The two ambitions for research on agroecology transition

To be able to achieve a successful transition process towards agroecology, many burdens have to be overcome by developing and implementing demanding ambitions while still solving often claimed disadvantages of agroecology, such as decreased income for farmers, limited use of land, greater time efforts within the whole food chain and complicated usage of technologies users might not be familiar with. Therefore, the first ambition is ecologically focused and aims to achieve sustainable interactions between single elements and their integration into ecosystems, whether on field or landscape scale. The underlying assumption is that a diversity of actors, but also varieties/breeds or species will be better adapted to heterogeneous and changing environments due to the continuous interactions between them. Their arrangements in time and space may also prove to be more efficient, because they not only seek out water and mineral resources better, but are also more resilient to disturbances because of their very diversity. Research in agroecology is therefore very much oriented towards analysis of living organisms, adaptability of varieties/breeds and species, the nature and importance of interactions between individuals and the abiotic environment, and their association effects at supra-individual scales in order to ultimately identify the best arrangements and combinations, help manage them and characterise the ecosystem functions and services that result from them. So, a systems approach is needed (see in particular annex 1 figure 1, right side of the mind map).

The second ambition is to open our agri-food chain actors to more diversity, more capacities to deal with specific situations, and to follow socio-technical trajectories across diverse economic sectors, through transitions or clean breaks (ruptures) with the past. Indeed, changing practices demands new information and technical capacities, such as the ones used to choose the cropping system for example, specific skills, learning and experiential processes. For agroecology transition, there is a need to develop capacity on different levels from the farm to the food system by (i) sharing of experiences and step-by-step learning, and (ii) identifying new possibilities and risks, and being prepared to manage uncertainties throughout the process. Agroecology is a path based more on the use of processes and principles than on specific standards and labels. Indicators will have to be created to follow this path. They will be essential for the accurate information of consumers and policy makers, and the involvement of the numerous stakeholders in the systemic transition (see annex 1 figure 1, left side of the mind map).

These two ambitions have in common the aim for more sustainable food production and consumption, in line with the concept of ecosystem services and human, economic and sociological dimensions that are accepted, recognised, or even encouraged, in the territory concerned. More specifically, the common aim can be, for example, the production of pesticide-free products, animal welfare, the consumption of local products, the possibility to reduce meat in the diet...all these interact and require an integrative management. One possibility to tackle and reach these aims is to identify the underpinning system of values, recognised by society, as a common background for the evolution of the entire agri-food system. These values can underpin specific recommendations in order to achieve the aims for the transition process (see in particular annex 1 figure 5).

3. From recommendations for agroecology transition to indicators for action

To foster the process of agroecology transition, we need sets of indicators that can detect specific elements about what is essential for agroecology up-scaling, and to do it at different scales from the farm level to the food system level and involving stakeholders from the policy-makers to the farmer.

Therefore, we compared the recommendations for agroecology transition published by a broad range of organisations, research institutes, as well as statements and review papers linked to the transition aspect: FAO (2018, 2019); HLPE (2019); CIDSE (2018); Gliessman (2016); Agroecology criteria tool (2019); Declaration of the International Forum for Agroecology (2015). We found that the recommendations to initiate and support agroecological transition had specific aspects in common throughout most of the studies, accordingly: i) promoting specific activities and ii) incentivising through policies. We built two mind maps (figure 2 and 3 Annex 1), one specifying the main categories of activities that could strengthen the transition, the other pointing out the diverse intentions of policy incentives. Mind maps are specific diagrams for representing tasks, words, concepts, or items linked to and arranged around a central concept or subject which give the advantage to allow structuring of information, analysis and the generation of new ideas and concepts. Those maps helped us to identify the core/common values justifying changes in activities and policy incentives (see figure 5 annex 1). The values which had been identified through the mind-mapping process represent the drivers of the transition process of the communities and stakeholders that are or have to be engaged in the “redesign of the systems” for agroecology transition. They are considered as useful as they denote the degree of importance of a specific action. The transition process might only be successful if all participating actors are convinced by its importance and necessity and that their values and principles of thinking and behaviour are represented. Hence, the human values, that also evolve, can be seen as the orientation that leads to following up with specific activities. The values that were found to underpin the policy incentives are levers to revisit current regulations used by policy makers to strengthen the transition process while preserving the common goods (e.g. through public stimulation). We found that the main components of the activities and policy incentives could be grouped to better link the two facets that have to be combined regarding the two ambitions of agroecology transition, evolution of agroecosystems and their environmental context on the one side, and the consideration of the socio-economic and cultural context on the other. In view of taking into account the needs of the actors engaged or to be engaged in agroecology transition, we also built a set of competences and skills to be mobilised and developed at the individual and collective levels for agroecology transition.

Specific skills and competences pertaining to the various actors of the value chain need to be present, accomplished through training and sharing of knowledge. We began with a list of competences for farmers that are needed to support them in their transition. However, this list is largely applicable to all actors in the food system (scientists, policy makers, citizens and NGO, farmers and farmer organisations...) (Debruyne et al. 2016; Taragola 2021). We grouped the list under the four categories outlined in the table of the competences and skills of the XXI’s century (Chalkiadaki 2018): i) knowledge and information, ii) digital literacy, iii) social skills and iv) personal skills. Then we linked the different skills to the map of the “activities” so that stakeholders can figure out sequences of competences and skills acquisition, and pointed out accurate training processes in order to do so (Anderson, 2019).

The mind maps including the values, activities, policies and competences for agroecology transition were submitted to evaluation and inputs during a two-hour long workshop grouping around 80 stakeholders (mainly representatives of European organisations such as farmers’ associations, European technology platforms and scientific initiatives). The objective of the workshop was to build and get feedback on this paper. Input from the participants during the workshop should make it more robust, complete and supported by the agroecological research

community. The aim was to validate and refine the activities, the values, the competences and the policy incentives that characterise or are necessary for agroecological transition. Hence, the participants helped to complete, improve and adjust the different mind-maps based on their knowledge, recommendations and known requirements for agroecology transition in order to develop this draft. Furthermore, we tried to implement and clarify aspects and definitions that were not clear to the participants. The four following tables resume the main items.

4. Values, activities, policies and competences to support agroecology transition

4.1 Key values underpinning activities and incentive policies

Firstly, we have identified the main values and common understanding and factors orienting the recommendations for developing activities and incentivisation policies to sustain agroecology transition. We grouped, on one side, the main principles, convictions and internal beliefs that support action and on the other side, motives and drivers that should be supported by the policies and further developed to ensure and orient a successful transition process.

Table 1: Values to support agroecology transition and considerations to incentivise them

To take action	To incentivise
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regeneration of ecosystems and ecosystem services • Land and natural resource governance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve biodiversity preservation • Preserve soil and land
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social values associated to the diet and traditional food culture • High food quality • Energy and timber as goods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure the right to adequate food for every human
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fairness and care of nature • Equity and social well-being of rural livelihoods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guarantee collective right and access to the commons • Insure inclusion and consideration of diversity • Strengthen local empowerment
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-creation of knowledge and participation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote diversity of knowledge • Clarify and insure data access and openness

4.2 Activities

The main categories of activities for AE transition are organised in two pillars, as are the recommendations for the design of policy incentives (Table 3), one dealing with the agroecosystem and environmental context and the second with the socio-economic and cultural context. Below, we find actions that should be considered to improve and protect social, economic and cultural values, such as human livelihoods, equity and social well-being. Under the category “agroecosystem and environmental context”, we find processes that are undertaken within the agroecosystem and which aim to improve environmental conditions that are important for sustainable food and agricultural systems. For agroecology transition, actions to improve the environmental conditions at the agroecosystem level are taking into account the overall social, economic and cultural context, and vice-versa.

Table 2: Activities that support AE transition. The two pillars are strongly linked and have to interact with each other; they can be specified at different levels within the system (farms, territories...)

Socio-economic and cultural context	Agroecosystem and environmental context
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop co-creation and participation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - through knowledge sharing and collaboration; - through welcoming tacit and implicit knowledge and knowledge of local communities - Foster participation of multi-stakeholders at local and global scales • Develop responsible governance mechanisms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - at local, regional, national and global scales, - involve the people from the food system from producer to end-user - value the commons - be inclusive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop synergies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - that enhance key functions across diversified agricultural and food systems - that use the complementarities between the elements of the agroecosystems - that use landscape planning and management • Develop efficiency <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - produce more using fewer external resources - manage the resources for reduced inputs - recycle - look for substitution with alternate systems and practices

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider cultural needs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - food habits and traditions - human connections to ensure food and nutrition security - the spiritual and material relationship with the land and environment • Develop fair and circular economy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - that reconnects producers and consumers within sustainable boundaries - improve solidarity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve resilience <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - of people, communities and ecosystems against disturbances - strengthen long term management of soil, plant and animal health, biodiversity - diversify • Adapt to climate change • Opt for recycling to decrease economic and environmental costs
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4.3 Policy incentives

The different dimensions which should be considered by policy makers in order to support AE transition are presented according to the two same tables as for activities, i) cultural, social and economic context and ii) agroecosystem and environmental context. Regarding the socio-cultural-economic context, incentives are aimed to support food sovereignty as well as offering opportunities for greater participation and co-creation. Regarding the agroecosystem and environmental context, policies intend either to regulate (the use of resources) or to reward proper agricultural management. For agroecology transition, incentives have to be designed according to the two pillars; for example, policies for improving the environmental conditions at the agroecosystem level should go along with policies encouraging co-creation. Moreover, the coherency and relevant combination of activities and policy incentives ensure an efficient and successful transition process.

Table 3: Policy incentives to support AE transition

Socio-economic and cultural context	Agroecosystem and environmental context
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage participatory approach at each level <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collective management - From local to global • Decentralise <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strengthen local empowerment and favour local adaptive management - Sensitive to local and regional demand • Promote food sovereignty • Link AE policies to global challenges <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Think also in terms of decent jobs for youth - Consider practices and interest of small-scale producers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulate/Legislate <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - E.g. quality seeds, agricultural products (labelling) - Better integrated resource management: water, soil, biodiversity - Emissions • Reward <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enhancement of biodiversity; biological pest control; creation and maintenance of natural habitats - Climate change mitigation, soil carbon storage, reduce soil tillage

4.4 Skills, knowledge and abilities for new competences

The competences were grouped into four categories of skills: i) knowledge and information competences fulfil the needs for the actors to understand the meaning, background and details of actions that are required within the transition process, from theoretical knowledge to why and how to act in the field; ii) social skills are based on communication and interaction between the different participants that are included in the transition process; iii) personal skills reflect the abilities developed through experience and deliberate practice of each of the single participants and less between them; iv) digital literacy represents the skills needed to use and handle digital devices, technologies, communication applications, and networks to access and manage information. We identified the sets of competences according to the activities that are foreseen to be developed by the different actors of the value chain, at the system level. Some of them are more needed by the producer than by the consumer, for example, but it is more a matter of specificity and depth of the training than an exclusion of some actors from any topic. It is also necessary to consider more diverse (and collective) ways to develop such competences. Those recommended for AE transition are: i) horizontal training (e.g. peer to peer), ii) networking, iii) dialogue between different sources of knowledge and iv) bringing political awareness along with practical training.

Table 4: Competences: skills, knowledge and abilities for AE transition. The two pillars are strongly linked and have to interact with each other. They can be treated at different levels (farm, territories...)

Socio-economic and cultural context	Agroecosystem and environmental context
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social skills <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication, collective management, capacity to network - Cultural and global awareness • Personal skills <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Critical thinking - Creativity - Openness - Self-development and autonomy - Adaptability and risk-taking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge and information competences <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Components of agroecological farming - Systems knowledge - Appropriate technologies - Food system - Actors' knowledge - Innovation processes - Understanding climate change • Agricultural equipment and digital techniques

We do not consider that for every organisation all the values, activities, policies and competences need to be fulfilled to be part of a successful agroecology transition process. Nevertheless, there are some criteria and indicators that could be seen as fundamental within each of the tables above that should be involved in the transition process as they play an essential role and therefore should not be missed. These specific criteria which need to be defined should help to identify organisations through a mapping process that could be useful to visualise the current state of development in agroecology transition across Europe as well as to develop a broader network that fosters the transition. Criteria are being developed by the ALL-Ready project as a complement to the present paper.

5. Research Infrastructures and Living Labs to accelerate agroecology transition

Accelerating AE transition means developing activities, designing policies and developing skills and competences for the transformation of the overall agroecosystem. Based on our previous analysis (the 4 tables), we understand that significant advances are made when both the agroecosystem and the environmental, socio-economic and cultural contexts are considered simultaneously. For example (see Table 2), opting for practices that use the complementarities between the elements of the agroecosystem to enhance synergies, will be easier in organisations facilitating participation and co-creation, and having in mind the cultural needs of the concerned territory. In general, changing practices with co-creation and participative processes favours the acceleration of AE transition. Assessing advances will also depend on the capacity to monitor the changes and impacts at the whole agroecosystem

level. Two main arrangements appear suited to shape, share, and renew the collective efforts and investments:

- Living labs, which are open innovation arrangements complying with three principles: i) co-creation, ii) user-centered, iii) in real life conditions,
- Research infrastructures, which are open research facilities for experimentation at different scales (plot, farm, landscape level and networks).

Living Labs appeared during 2000 as real-life testing and experimentation environments for developing information and communication technologies (ICT) (Følstad, 2008). In practice, living labs place the user and the citizen at the centre of innovation and operate as intermediaries among citizens, research organisations, companies, cities and regions for joint value co-creation, rapid prototyping or validation to scale up innovation and businesses. In LLs, three categories of outcomes are co-produced: business, social and knowledge (Dubé et al., 2014). Since 2000, the fields of application of LLs have multiplied (Hossain et al., 2019). In Europe, LLs are increasingly central for implementing sustainable transition, for instance, in urban development, health infrastructure, education campuses, rural development... LLs appear to be both practice-driven organisations that facilitate and foster open, collaborative innovation, as well as real-life environments or arenas where both open innovation and user innovation processes can be studied and subject to experiments and where new solutions are developed. The three operational principles characterizing LLs (i) co-creation, ii) user-centered, iii) in real life conditions) are diversely implemented to be adapted to the socio-economical sector in which they are implemented. ENoLL, the European Network of Living Labs, founded in 2006, supports the evolution and the uptake of the Living Lab paradigm worldwide and has developed a labelling process. According to ENoLL, 5 key elements must be present in a living lab, regardless of their application domain:

- Active user involvement (i.e. Empowering end users to have an impact on the innovation process);
- Real-life setting (i.e. Testing and experimenting “in the wild”);
- Multi-stakeholder participation (i.e. The involvement of producers, technology providers, service providers, relevant institutional actors, professional or residential end users);
- A multi-method approach (i.e. The combination of methods and tools originating from e.g. Ethnography, psychology, sociology, strategic management, engineering);
- Co-creation (i.e. Iterations of design cycles with different sets of stakeholders).

LLs develop unique features in line with their application domains. Highlighting such specific features helps practitioners to better understand their implementation, operational challenges and opportunities. It will help identify the needs in terms of exchange of experience, empowerment, outscaling...that the European network will have to address. . In the agricultural sector, LLs are rapidly developing worldwide (International Agroecosystem Living Laboratories Working Group, 2019). McPhee and colleagues (2021) have specified the unique features of agroecosystems LL, by analyzing their commonalities and differences with other categorised LLs. First, agroecosystem living labs were found to belong to the “family of place-based LLs”, along with urban and rural living labs. Then the categories developed by Steen and van Bueren in 2017 for urban living labs (i. aims, ii. participants, iii. activities, iv. context) were used to identify commonalities and particularities (see below). To infer the unique features of LLs for agroecology transition, we choose a similar strategy. The characteristics of agroecosystem LLs, their closest relatives, were used as an initial framework (see figure 6 annex 1) to gather experiential and academic knowledge that will help us specify their commonalities and differences. This was done during a workshop gathering all the partners from ALL-Ready and their expertise in AE transition, LL and RI.

Research Infrastructures (RIs) have largely evolved the last years, thanks to the evolution of the research questions and capacities and also to strong political motivation to fund and give value to common tools. In this sense, the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI), established in 2002, has had an essential role in the development of an European approach to research infrastructure policy as a key element of the European Research Area (ERA). As a result, a rich landscape of RIs has been established, covering all scientific domains, with over 50 European Research Infrastructures mobilising close to € 20 billion worth of common investments. ESFRI has facilitated common investment at regional, national and European levels, reinforcing Europe's global leadership in this endeavor. (ESFRI WHITE PAPER, 2020, www.ec.europa.eu/research/infrastructures). Europe's RIs boost the capacity to deliver scientific breakthroughs, that at the same time foster innovation. RIs can support research to rapidly address the societal challenges facing Europe and the world and can be key to lead and prepare the necessary economic, social and environmental transitions. (ESFRI WHITE PAPER, 2020, www.ec.europa.eu/research/infrastructures). As a result, interdisciplinary training and innovation are now strong activities of research infrastructures. They are indispensable assets to understand socio-economic and ecological processes from an academic point of view. They are unique assets to follow the complex design and to redesign the production and ecological systems that AE transition moves forward, provided that they are and will open to more diverse users. Knowing the main characteristics and evolution of RIs, we infer what will be well suited for AE transition (see figures 8 and 9 annex 1).

LL and RI, hand in hand, should form efficient instruments to accelerate AE transition.

5.1 The unique features of living labs for agroecology transition

Knowing the requisites for AE transition mentioned in tables 1 and 2, and the three principles of living labs (co-creation, user-centered and in real-life conditions), we can infer that LLs will help the transition through:

- Enlarging the diversity of actors involved in the transition process, from the producer to the academics, from the farmer to the citizen, from agriculture to the overall food chain;
- Rapidly empowering the relevant actors thanks to the co-creation process and the intensity with which knowledge is exchanged;
- Taking into account "place-based", and the power of a network to outscale at a more global level;
- Creating momentum for interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approaches.

Our purpose is to screen initiatives that can be future pivots of agroecology transitions in Europe, benefiting from and contributing to the network of LL and RI to be implemented. Therefore, we need to infer what will be the unique features that will discriminate LL for agroecology transition among other place-based living labs. In the following section, we present the: i) aim, ii) participants, iii) activities and iv) context of place-based LLs as studied in McPhee et al. (2021), and specify what will be unique in LLs for AE transition based on the collective expertise of ALL-Ready consortium.

5.1.1 Aim

Living labs, by definition, produce three categories of values: business, knowledge and social (Dubé et al., 2014), "knowledge" meaning that LLs promote co-learning among the stakeholders and partners engaged. In this way, they serve to support organisational and social transformations.

Place-based LLs, whether they are related to urban or rural development or agroecosystems, additionally aim to improve sustainability and resilience of the socio-ecosystem to which they apply (see McPhee et al. 2021 for references).

Living labs for AE transition will work towards improving sustainability and resilience not only at the agroecosystem level, but also at landscape level and considering the food system as a whole. Their specificity will be that they will favor options considering biodiversity of the “place” and in the surroundings. One of their main purposes will be to gather the different actors around the preservation of the environment as common goods.

What will make LLs for AE transition unique will thus be:

- Their very strong local embeddedness;
- The large diversity of their origins, from networks or communities willing to develop new practices to arrangements developed under incitative policies, as well as the diversity of the actors and stakeholders involved (farmers, policy makers, consumers, citizens...);
- The heterogeneity and intensity of knowledge produced (from practice to policies).

5.1.2 Activities

Three key activities characterise the innovation process in LLs: co-creation, demonstration and iteration with the following sequence: experimentation-evaluation-improvement of the experimentation (Dubé et al., 2014).

Place-based LLs, because of their aim to improve the sustainability and resilience of the socio-ecosystem to which they apply, due to their local anchorage, exhibit additional activities linked to their concern with the environmental impact. They need and produce large sets of knowledge and data to describe the system of concern, monitor and share the improvements in terms of resilience and sustainability. The demonstration and evaluation activities rapidly extend the local level. They develop specific outreach and networking activities to scale out and up their own achievements (Mc Phee et al. 2021).

In LLs for AE transition, we infer that the activities linked to the scaling out and up will be even more intensive than in agroecosystem LLs. The participants in the living lab to stay involved or to convince are either the actors of the whole value chain, or those concerned by the landscape or the territorial development. The more mature LLs for agroecology transition will be particularly knowledge intensive, and will be attentive to having inclusive approaches. The occurrence of transgenerational initiatives and activities may also be indicators of their level of maturity. Tacit and implicit knowledge will enter into play and more generally the knowledge used and produced will be very diverse and heterogeneous.

Living labs for AE transition will have to develop, more than other place-based LLs, due to the large heterogeneity of the actors and the knowledge used and produced, governance schemes to specifically:

- Avoid the burden of information over a so large system and set of actors;
- Manage conflicts of interest and deal with various ideologies;
- Orchestrate the co-creation among actors that do not know/ understand each other;
- Ensure the democratic orientation of the direction taken (towards common goods).

The demonstration and iteration activities will demand a strong and dedicated effort, for which the experience and know-how of multi-actor innovation processes is an asset. The targets and the means have to be evaluated in real time, with an evaluation process which can evolve according to the collective learning.

The activities in LLs for AE transition will be very dependent on the quantity and diversity of data that will be needed to characterise and monitor the changes at the overall system level. Managing and producing accurate data will be crucial to maintain the involvement of the actors, all concerned by the evaluation of the impact of new practices at the whole system level.

The innovation activity in LLs for AE transition will be characterised by its strong dependence on seasonal cycles (as a characteristic of living processes, climate...), with their short and long-term impacts. In addition, compared to other LLs and place-based LLs, those for AE transition will have to be particularly long lasting and to be able to absorb unpredictable variations.

5.1.3 Participants

In LLs, participants are a mix of private and public organisations, academics and “users”.

In place-based LLs, the users vary with the socio-system to which they apply, and can be different at each iteration step, the final user being the “citizen”. For example, in agroecosystem LLs, the user can be either the farmer, the consumer or the citizen.

In LLs for AE transition, the notion of user will be particularly diverse: the adviser, the farmer, the consumer, the citizen... and their role will evolve even more than in agroecosystem LLs, because of the drivers of the transition (see Table 1), which imply opening the evaluation of the impact to the overall landscape or food system. Moreover, it may happen that LLs for AE transition develop based on networks of farmers willing to experiment new practices, or on the will of local authorities to promote AE transition. The LLs for AE transition will have to constantly revisit who will be their users and to work on their openness to consumers and citizens.

In LLs, the funding is highly variable, generally a balance of public and private funds, but sometimes only one of the two. In LLs for AE transition, as for other place-based LLs, the governmental investment will be determinant. Researchers, due to the relatively high number and diversity of partners that have to be involved, will have diverse roles:

- Provide scholarly knowledge;
- Design a comprehensive support for the “metagovernance” scheme that is necessary to maintain the engagement of the diverse key actors in the territories and along the entire value chain;
- Be part of the decision-making and even facilitate collective decisions.

5.1.4 Context

All LLs operate in a “real-life” context.

For place-based LLs, the “real life” is the system, the complexity of the landscape, of the real communities concerned. The boundaries are the limits conferred by the biophysics of the place concerned as well as of the economic or socio-technical system considered.

For LLs for AE transition, the boundaries will be the ones of the agroecosystem, plus its surroundings (territory), plus optionally the one of the food system. With such open consideration, there will be surely mismatches. Besides the “place”, the context of LLs for AE transition will be marked by the strong implication of researchers because of the large sets of knowledge needed and of the shifts of paradigms required by AE. It also will be also marked by the strong involvement of the diverse actors forming the so-called ‘agriculture knowledge and innovation system’ (AKIS, gathering teachers, researchers, advisers, policy makers and practitioners), and the enlargement of the AKIS to new players.

For all those reasons, it will be essential to register the origin (conditions of emergence, actors, networks, incentives, policies) of the LL for AE transition to characterise its potential.

First, it will help to link with the aim and orientations of the regulatory framework and policies that incentivise its emergence (see Table 3 for specification) and second, to infer the level of maturity of the LL regarding its driving force towards AE transition at the landscape, territorial or overall food system level.

5.2 The contribution of research infrastructure (RI) for agroecology transition

5.2.1 Context

A general definition we can adopt of RIs is given by the Directorate-General for Research European Commission (UE: https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/european-research-infrastructures_en)

“Research Infrastructures are facilities that provide resources and services for research communities to conduct research and foster innovation. They can be used beyond research e.g. for education or public services and they may be single-sited, distributed, or virtual. They include: major scientific equipment or sets of instruments; collections, archives or scientific data; computing systems and communication networks; any other research and innovation infrastructure of a unique nature which is open to external users”.

The [RISCAPE project](#) on research infrastructures stresses that the RI must provide facilities, resources or related services to researchers, also from outside of the Research Infrastructure institution itself, i.e. to act as providers of services to researchers, not to act as researching institutions. This project stresses the purpose of the RI services which must be to conduct or facilitate research and must also have some degree of longevity (short term projects with no long-term longevity or sustainability plans, and which would only have a very brief use period are therefore excluded).

5.2.2 Aim

RI can be defined as facilities, in a very broad sense, that provide services for research communities, whether or not they are managed by research institutions, working in a long-term perspective, applying FAIR principles (Guiding Principles for scientific data management: Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets).

Thus, we can characterise them by the main criteria as following:

- Long-term and FAIR principles;
- Size of the research community that use facilities and services;
- Diversity of facilities, of data, of contexts that allow scientific production;
- Innovation, education, public services contribution.

RIs can be facilities for agroecology transition. They are dedicated to research communities, and allow scientists to observe / experiment / predict agroecosystem and agri-food redesign. All together they contribute to bringing a corpus of scientific knowledge on agroecology available for agroecology transition. They can contribute to:

- Various degrees of agriculture and agri-food redesign (from incremental to strong redesign, gradient of biodiversity in agroecosystems);
- Sustainability assessment (impacts, ecosystem services, ecological, social and economic dimensions);
- Vulnerability - Adaptability - Resilience assessment (emergent properties of agroecosystems);

- Dynamics of the agroecology transition.

5.2.3 Activities

RIs for agroecology transition are diverse: RIs on national or European roadmaps; systemic and innovative experiments; modelling / multicriteria assessment (life cycle analysis tools); e-Infrastructure that provide data, metadata and services. Examples are detailed below. Considering the level of integration (farm, landscape), interdisciplinary and the dynamic orientation of the RIs (system changing) are important for agroecology transition. Information systems (ISs), including metadata, data, experiences have been developed for most of them, as a condition on National and European RI.

As examples, we can cite Emphasis (plant phenotyping) or ANAEE (soil-plant systems) which are labelled as RIs at European level and are focused on agroecosystem functioning at species, plant, plot level; they provide rich information on agroecology, particularly on the basic processes involved for agroecology (interactions between biotic processes), but their contribution to agroecology transition is moderate and often poorly mobilised for transition. Moreover, these platforms are not dedicated to monitor complex interactions in agroecological transition in the making.

Another example, eLTER (European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research Infrastructure; socio-ecosystem monitoring at landscape level) can bring holistic information on the co-evolution of farm or landscape transitions and ecosystem services (including biomass production). Such platforms, despite not being designed as agroecology experiments, bring information on agroecological transition, because of long-term observations of socio-ecosystems, including agroecological transition at farm and landscape level (Silva and Tchamitchian 2018).

As part of the ESFRI Roadmap, LifeWatch ERIC devoted to Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research with applications, is a distributed e-Infrastructure that implements e-Services to address the big environmental challenges and support knowledge-based strategic solutions to environmental preservation. LifeWatch ERIC has developed a specific strategy to support agroecology transition through the co-design and co-development of specific Virtual Research Environments applied to agroecology research.

Systemic innovative experiments on research farms managed by and for research, including redesign of cropping systems, animal-crop systems, orchard systems, or landscape design, or even agri-food systems, etc. could be considered as RIs that are fully relevant for agroecological transition, because they analyse transition in the making, including a redesign of systems and long-term monitoring to understand the processes involved in a redesign. In such experiments, stakeholders are more and more involved. This can be useful to test what we cannot test in a real-life situation (strong redesign for example).

Multi-performance assessment tools (Life Cycle Analysis) or modelling (crop models...) and simulations of scenarios can be considered as useful because they can predict the effect of redesigning systems, if data are available to test them. In this regard, innovative decision support systems can help to support knowledge based decision-making process for the management of agroecosystems for farmers and policy makers. They are sometimes included in RIs and some of them really use FAIR principles for data & software management.

Some hybrid approaches, between research and society, useful for farmers and farmers' networks, for citizens and for research can also be considered. Research can bring and collect knowledge in such hybrid settings. Some of them are not so far from LLs. Examples include networks of farms at regional or national level, (even a few farms in a small territory), citizen science, platforms with innovation tools and experience (serious games...), i.e., platforms where innovation is more or less collectively in the making, and where scientists are involved. An academic production cannot be easily recognized in such networks because of difficulties in providing generic knowledge, sufficient data sets... But they can be fully considered as

open innovations for agroecology. Such hybrids can be mapped as RI if research is involved (this involvement can be low) and knowledge produced.

All these facilities and services, including hybrids, can be useful to LLs, bringing to them academic knowledge, analytical as well systemic knowledge. Conversely, LLs can ask scientific questions that can be investigated by RIs.

5.2.4 Participants

RI for agroecology is mainly dedicated to scientific activities, and the main participants are scientists. RI can be initiated, managed or partly managed by research. We can underline that, in many countries, such platforms are not installed or managed by research but by agricultural organizations or research and development organizations.

They are often used also for teaching, with students, agricultural and environmental managers. They can provide useful information for stakeholders, if scientific knowledge is transformed into useful information for them and can also provide multiple services to a large community of actors in an open science vision. In most of them, innovation is developed (testing new sensors, technologies...). Stakeholders are more or less involved, as an example to contribute to discuss observations, or experiments in RI.

5.2.5 Conclusions

In this paper, we define the main requirements for agroecology transition from the socio-economic to environmental context, and describe how living labs and research infrastructures are specifically suited to achieve this transition. In particular, we detail how the concept of place-based living labs and agroecosystem living labs can be taken one step further to build living labs for agroecology transition. We also define what we mean by research infrastructures in a broad sense and how they can also support agroecology transition. The concepts developed in this paper are a foundation on which to build the next steps toward a European network of living labs and research infrastructures, including:

- Developing inclusion criteria for relevant LLs and RIs,
- Mapping and analysis of existing LLs and RIs,
- Piloting a network,
- Engaging all types of stakeholders,
- Developing a capacity building programme,
- Creating means for data and knowledge sharing, through a Virtual Research Environment,
- Communicating on the different elements of the project and the pilot network
- Proposing governance, funding models and finally a roadmap for the network.

All these elements will contribute to the European partnership which is being developed under Horizon Europe and thereby contribute to meeting European policy goals such as the Green Deal and the CAP.

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Annex 1: Methods and steps to build the conceptual framework to specify the activities needed for the agroecology transition and identify the unique features of living labs operating it

The work intertwined three sources of materials:

- Scientific foresights for agroecology;
- Policy foresights for agroecology transition;
- The unique features of living labs and research infrastructures;

For each source, the team in charge of task 1.1 prepared a representation in the form of mind maps of the main subjects and outcomes identified in the literature, after having screened as many diverse sources as possible; it was subjected to evaluation with the consortium of ALL-Ready with two expected outcomes, the precision and share of ownership of the framework.

The results were summarized to be shared with the stakeholders and get their input to refine the conceptual framework.

1st source: the essential questions for agroecology transition

The method was to depart from the burning research questions for the agroecology transition according to the literature and the consortium's knowledge and point of view.

The core themes and sub-subjects were firstly extracted from a recent scientific prospective undertaken by INRAE with an interdisciplinary high-level working group and were then completed with recent literature synthesis. This served as skeleton to organize the 1st WP1 workshop with the members of the ALL-Ready consortium. In practice, the synthesis of the literature was presented as a mind map, open to the contribution to each of the members of the consortium and collective discussion (figure 1)

2nd source, the essential activities accelerate the agroecology transition

The diversity of policy papers, scientific synthesis and publications of high level panels were then revisited to bring the recommendations under the same frame, having in mind that it should be compatible with what was identified at the end of the 1st step (figure 1).

It was obvious that all recommendations had in common three main dimensions, the values that were driving the changes, the activities that will produced an impact, to be undertaken at the socio ecosystem level and at the political level. First, we concentrated our analysis on the activities and produced the two following mind maps:

Figure 2: The activities that, according to the policy papers will mark the agroecology transition ; on the right, the activities to be undertaken at the ecosystem level and on the left, the socio-economic conditions that should surround

Figure 3: The different categories of policies that could help accelerate the agroecology transition; on the right, concerning the practice at the ecosystem level and on the left, the socio-economic surrounding.

We checked that our categories (figures 5 and 6) did not miss any of the main activities outlined by Gliessman which were symbolized to be good reminders (figure 7). The “5 levels” were not taken as levels, but as indications of the activities that mark the inscription in the agroecology transition.

Figures 4 a and B: The categories of activities that mark the agroecology transition according to Gliessman (2016) used to check the initial quality of the mind maps

Then we were able to identify the values that were common to all recommendations, that orient specifically the way activities are undertaken and policies are shapes.

Figure 5: The main values and principles of action that are common to diverse sets of recommendations for the agroecological transition

3rd source, the unique features of living labs and research infrastructures for accelerating the agroecology transition

Regarding living labs.

The features of the living labs evolves with their application field. To infer what are or will be the characteristics of living labs that accelerate the agroecology transition, the members of the consortium were trained to be more familiar with the unique characteristics of agroecosystem living labs before a brainstorming session was organized. They were invited to complete the aims, context, participants and activities, that will distinguish the living labs for the agroecology transition from the agroecosystem living labs.

We were then able to represent the unique features of living labs fit for accelerating the transition in such synthetic way:

Brainstorming session Dec 2020

Figure 7: copy of the slide used in subsequent meetings with partner projects to share the on-going development of the framework

Research Infrastructures

We departed from a very general representation of what research infrastructures are and what they are aiming at:

[Research infrastructures]

Definition: facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields. Here we would look at research infrastructures that can be considered to support agroecological innovation.

Figure 8: Description of the usual functions of research infrastructure to introduce the reflexion on their role along with living labs for accelerating the agroecology transition.

Then, based on the previous outcomes, we opted for entries that will help us differentiate the complementarities between research infrastructures and living labs as such: their working principles, their outcomes in terms of values, their aim, context, participants and activities.

Figure 9: the distinctions between what living labs and research infrastructures can bring to the innovation process

The presentation of the draft of the framework to the stakeholders

The frameworks were presented at the first workshop with the stakeholder in the following way: first the values, then the activities and then the kind of policies that will support the transition, before inferring specific roles of living labs and research infrastructures in the acceleration of the agroecological transition.

The stakeholders were invited to discuss, evaluate and complete the accurateness of the framework.

And their potential roles of Living labs and research infrastructures for the acceleration of the agroecology transition could be outlined thanks to the framework as such:

In addition, on the request of WP5 leaders, the framework was also used to specify the set of skills and competences that will make the difference, based on the scientific and grey literature taking the common categories of the skills of the XXI'st (personal skills, social skills, digital literacy and knowledge and information acquisition) and requests from practitioners engaged in the agroecology transition.

